

Breast cancer championship phase V4

ID: fb77161-ed71-4983-a49f-1a22c717f32f

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/fb77161-ed71-4983-a49f-1a22c717f32f/details>

Creation date: 2024-01-04 05:57:44.823696+00:00

License: CHAIMELEON Consortium 1.0 [<https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/web/terms-and-conditions.pdf>]

Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 1505

Subjects count: 1236

Age range: Between 27 years and 97 years

Sex: Female, Unkown

Body part(s): BREAST, HEAD, ABDOMEN, CHEST, MAMOGRAFIA, Unknown

Modality: MG, MR, CT, CR, Unknown